

Development of FRP Composites with Excellent Erosion Resistance by Solid Particles

D.N. QIAN ^a, L.M. BAO ^b, M.Y. TAKATERA ^b and A.H. YAMANAKA ^c

^aDepartment of Bioscience and Textile Technology, Interdisciplinary Graduate School of Science and Technology Shinshu University, 3-15-1, Tokida, Ueda-shi, Nagano, 386-8567, Japan

Email: s08t108@shinshu-u.ac.jp

^b Faculty of Textile Science and Technology, Shinshu University, 3-15-1, Tokida, Ueda-shi, Nagano, 386-8567, Japan

^c Research Center, Toyobo Co, Ltd., 2-1-1, Katata, Ohtsu, Shiga, 520-0292, Japan

SUMMARY

The solid particle erosion behaviors of CF/GF hybrid FRPs and DFRP under various impact angles were carried out for comparison with CFRP, GFRP and matrix resin. It was concluded that it was feasible to develop the FRP materials with low density, high strength, and excellent particle erosion resistance.

Keywords: Solid particle, FRPs, Erosion Resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Solid particle erosion is one type of wear that causes local damage combined with the progressive loss of original material from a solid surface due to micro mechanical interaction between that surface and solid particles. It has been reported that the surfaces of FRP equipments operating in erosion environments were impacted by the solid particles contained in the air, which destroy the materials. According to literatures [1-6], it was widely recognized that polymers and their composites had poorer erosion resistance than metals, and that polymer composites containing reinforcement fiber (FRP) usually erode faster than neat polymers. In other words, the reinforcement fiber could enhance the strength of polymer composites, but reduced the erosion resistance of the polymer composites in generally.

In order to develop new high-cost performance FRP materials with high strength and excellent particle erosion resistance, this study investigated the erosion behavior of unidirectional CF/GF-FRPs hybrid materials as compared to GFRP and CFRP at first;

then tested the tensile strength and investigated the effect of impact angles on the erosion behavior of UD-DFRP (Dyneema[®] reinforced polymer composite), as compared to CFRP and matrix. It was feasible to develop FRP materials with high strength, low density and excellent erosion resistance by hybrid structure or new reinforcement fiber.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The UD-FRPs were constructed as unidirectional Carbon, Glass and Dyneema fiber for reinforcement respectively, with unsaturated polyester resin as matrix. The arrangement of the laminas in the hybrid specimens were shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Model of the erosion hybrid specimens

Erosion tester and test conditions

A schematic drawing of the erosion testing system was presented in Fig. 2. The specimen was fixed on the metal stage. Solid particles were held in a hopper, and fed into the air stream by a micro feeder (ME-1, Tsutsui Rikagaku Kikai Co. Ltd.). The velocity of compressed air, created by an air compressor was controlled by adjusting the inlet pressure of the gun nozzle (NAB-11-6, Trucso Nakayama Co. Ltd.). The high-velocity air stream containing solid particles was shot from the nozzle of the air gun and impacted the surface of the specimen, creating erosion wear.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of the erosion tester

Fig.3 Definition of impingement angle and fiber orientation

The distance between the air gun nozzle and the fiber was 40mm, and the inner diameter of the nozzle was 5.35mm. Erosion tests were performed by changing the angle between the air flow and the horizontal axis of the test specimen α , setting six stages (90°, 75°, 60°, 45°, 30° and 15°) at a fiber orientation of 90° as shown in Fig. 3, and testing was carried out after 20 minutes at a velocity of 128m/s. The solid particles used in the erosion tests were angular alumina abrasives with an average size of 11.5 μ m. The average erodent feed rate of particles was adjusted to a mixture ratio of 1.4g/min and 1.8g/min.

Tensile testing

Tensile tests of the FRP composites were conducted by Auto Graph (AG-20KND) with a load cell (SFL-20KNAG) manufactured by Shimadzu Corporation. The tensile speed is 2mm/min for CFRP, GFRP and 5mm/min for DFRP, respectively.

RESULTS

Erosion behaviors of CF/GF hybrid FRPs

After impact of every 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, and 40 minutes at the impact angle of 90°, the weight of the specimen was measured by a balance, respectively. Fig. 4 was the relationship between the weight of an impact particle on unit damaged area (W_c) and the weight loss of the specimens. W_c was calculated according to the following equation:

$$r_{impact} = \frac{r \left(\frac{g}{min} \right)}{n \times A \left(\frac{m^3}{min} \right)} \times n \left(\frac{m}{min} \right) = \frac{r}{A} \left(\frac{g}{m^2 \cdot min} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$W_c = r_{impact} \times t \left(\frac{g}{m^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where ρ_{impact} is the density of the impact particle; ρ is the weight of the particles in unit time; and v , A , t are the velocity of the stream, the impact area, and the exposure time, respectively.

Linear least-squares method revealed that the data for GF/CFRP was distributed around a line that did not pass through the origin as shown in Fig. 4. It was evident that the weight loss of GF/CFRP was no better than the GFRP during the initial period of composite eroding. With increasing exposure time, the difference between the materials containing CF and those not containing CF was easy to see. The average erosion resistance of the GF/CFRP is lower than the CF/GFRP under the whole testing period at the impact angle of 90°. It was revealed that the arrangement of the carbon lamina and the glass lamina has significantly influences on the erosive wear of composites.

Fig. 4 Weight loss as a function of the weight of an impact particle on unit area.

After impact of 20 minutes from 15 to 90°, almost all the interface between the first and second laminae of the specimens were penetrated through, and only the first interface between the CF and GF lamina was drilled through. Fig.5 illustrated the influence of the impact angles on weight loss of four kinds of specimens. The broken curves were gained from all of the examination values analyzed by two-stage least squares method. It can be seen that the weight loss values of hybrid materials were keeping in the middle of the GFRP and CFRP. And all of the maximum weight loss values were approaching to the impact angle of 60° in the broken curves. This was semi ductile erosion behavior [7].

Based on SEM micrographs, it was considered that the erosion mechanisms of CF and GF were not changed in hybrid materials and the erosion was owed to the damage of simple assembly of the CF and GF laminations.

Fig.5 Weight loss as a function of the impact angles.

Tensile strength and erosion resistance of DFRP

The average experiment results of tensile strength (σ_b) and elastic modulus (E_t) of four times for the three kinds of FRP composite were presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Data of the σ_b and E_t of 3 kinds of FRP.

Materials		CFRP(V_f : 30%)		DFRP (V_f : 28%)		GFRP(V_f : 44%)	
Properties		σ_b (MPa)	E_t (GPa)	σ_b (MPa)	E_t (GPa)	σ_b (MPa)	E_t (GPa)
Experimental results	Aver.	985.0	52.48	559.3	27.54	607.4	27.68
	Stde.	88.6	8.47	73.2	2.38	33.2	2.02
Compare values	Aver.	919.3	48.98	559.3	27.54	455.6	20.76
	Stde.	71.8	7.91	73.2	2.38	24.9	1.52

*The compared values in bold type are calculated following the V_f at 28%, in accordance with the DFRP.

In order to compare the mechanical properties of various reinforcement fibers, the specific tensile yield strength (indicated by ●) and specific elastic modulus (indicated by ■) were calculated and shown in Fig. 6. It was obvious that the specific tensile yield strength and the specific elastic modulus of DFRP were more than three times larger than those of GFRP, which were not markedly different from those of CFRP. Therefore, it was confirmed that the mechanical properties of the DFRP were equivalent to or better than those of the widely used CFRP and GFRP. Therefore, it is feasible to substitute DFRP for GFRP and CFRP as a stronger structural material.

Fig. 6 Comparison of specific tensile strength and specific elastic modulus of 3 kinds of FRP

Fig. 7 Comparison of the erosion rate for the DFRP, CFRP and matrix materials

In order to quantify the extent of the damage and in comparing the erosion of various types of materials, erosion rate of the volumetric loss (v) is defined by the following equation:

$$n = \frac{e}{r} = \frac{W_L(g)}{W_S(g) \times r} \quad (3)$$

Where ε is the erosion rate of weight loss; W_L is the weight loss of the specimen; W_s is the total weight of the impact particle in 20 minutes, and ρ is the density of the testing material.

Fig. 7 plotted the relationship between the erosion rate of volumetric loss and the impact angles from 15° to 90° for three kinds of materials. The higher the erosion rate, the worse erosion resistance of the testing materials. The erosion resistance of the CFRP was much larger than that of DFRP and the matrix. If the erosion rate of GFRP was drawn in this figure, it would be assumed to be higher than the curve of CFRP, once again confirming that the erosion resistance of CFRP and GFRP was not as great as that of the neat matrix.

The maximum erosion rate of the CFRP was at the impact angle of 60°, exhibiting a marked difference from that of DFRP and the matrix. However, the similarity in the tendency of both two curves was obvious. The maximum erosion rates of them approached the impact angle between 30° and 45°. Furthermore, the erosion rates of matrix for all impact angles were much higher than DFRP. In other words, the erosion resistance of DFRP was superior to the matrix resin. It was considered to be the attribution of the type of the reinforced fiber used.

CONCLUSIONS

The erosion of CF/GF hybrid FRPs were higher than that of CFRP but lower than that of GFRP. The arrangement of the carbon lamina and the glass lamina has significantly influences the erosion wear of composites. Furthermore, not only the mechanical properties of the DFRP were equivalent to or better than those of the widely used CFRP and GFRP, but also DFRP exhibited the excellent particle erosion resistance as compared to all specimens. It is feasible to develop the FRP materials with low density, high strength and excellent particle erosion resistance by hybrid structure with higher erosion resistance materials.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Grant-in-Aid for Global COE Program by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pool KV, Dharan CKH, Finnie I (1986) *Wear*, **107**, 1-12
- [2] Sundararajam G, Roy M, Venkataraman B (1990) *Wear*, **140**, 369-281
- [3] Roy M, Vishwanathan B, Sundararajan G (1994) *Wear*, **171**, 149-161
- [4] Harsha AP, Tewari US, Venkatraman B (2003) *Wear*, **254**, 693-712
- [5] Tewari US, Harsha AP, Häger AM, Friedrich K (2003) *Compos Sci Technol*, **63**, 549-577
- [6] Tewari US, Harsha AP, Häger AM, Friedrich K (2002) *Wear*, **252**, 992-1000
- [7] Häger A, Friedrich K, Dzenis YA, Paipetis SA (1995) “Study of erosion wear of advanced polymer composites”, pp155–162, in: K. Street, B.C. Whistler (Eds.), *Proceedings of the ICCM-10*, Canada Woodhead Publishing Ltd., Cambridge